

Adoption of Cloud Computing in Nigerian University Libraries: Challenges and Strategies

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Abstract

This study investigates the Adoption of Cloud Computing in Nigerian University Libraries: Challenges and Strategies. Cloud computing has transformed many libraries in terms of operations and service delivery. Adopting cloud technology has its challenges. Two objectives guided the study. A descriptive survey design was used, and the population is comprised of librarians and IT staff from federal and private university libraries in North Central, Nigeria. 178 Librarians and IT staff were used for this study. Results show that institutions' poor subscription ($X=3.37$) and staff resistance to change ($X=3.02$) are the top challenges associated with cloud computing technology and the overall mean ranking for continuous training of library professionals on emerging technologies was 3.69, while embracing change was ranked lowest. The respondents agreed that all these strategies could enhance cloud computing technology for effective library service delivery. Recommendations were offered, and a conclusion was made.

Keywords: Cloud Computing, Technology, Challenges, Strategies, University Libraries

Introduction

The advent of cloud computing has stirred up significant changes in various sectors globally, including the academic sphere. In the context of Nigerian university libraries, adopting cloud computing presents a promising avenue for enhancing effective service delivery, management of resources and overall operational Efficacy. Cloud computing, characterized by its provision of on-demand computing resources and services over the Internet, offers numerous advantages such as scalability, cost-effectiveness, and accessibility (Armbrust et al., 2020), bringing opportunities that would significantly change libraries' information service delivery landscape. Libraries must acknowledge technology trends and re-invent their services to remain relevant in the scheme of things (Irenea et al., 2018) while acknowledging that there would be challenges. Integrating cloud computing technologies into academic libraries in Nigeria is fraught with various challenges that necessitate strategic planning and implementation.

Librarians continue to face the issue of upgrading their skills and knowledge on the application of emerging technological innovation to enable them to render effective services to their patrons. This position is supported by Adetunji et al. (2020), who state that the university sector in sub-Saharan Africa has a high concentration of skilled human resources. Deploying cloud computing in libraries has the potential to become a force in transforming library services globally. Without information technology, the archaic practices within libraries would stifle growth, innovation and effective service delivery. Therefore, for university libraries to effectively apply cloud computing technology for effective library service delivery they must understand and have the skills required to use this emerging technological innovation to perform their routine services.

Over the years, much effort has been put in place to ensure effective library service delivery, from manual processes to the application of IT solutions. Unfortunately, many university libraries have been unable to achieve their desired goal. An automated library applies IT solutions to provide effective library services, while non-automated libraries can be referred to as analogue or manually operated libraries to provide library service. The existing automated libraries partially solved the problems of the existing manually operated libraries. However, there are still a lot of existing problems that need serious attention. These include Resource cost, deployment and maintenance cost, lack of technical knowledge and support, poor infrastructure, hazardous ICT waste, Inherent problems of an automated library, Less or absence of collaboration, and Less resource usage (CPU cycles) (Armbrust et al., 2009; Mohammed, 2015).

There are challenges militating against effective library service delivery today despite the availability of computerization and automation of library resources, as identified in some literature. These challenges include adopting cloud computing in libraries, which faces several significant challenges. These include unreliable WAN/LAN infrastructure, which is frequently susceptible to disruptions caused by fires, storms, and vandalism. Additionally, a notable shortage of computer-literate staff within libraries hinders the effective implementation and management of cloud technologies. The poor power generation state further exacerbates these issues, leading to inconsistent access and operational inefficiencies. Furthermore, libraries often lack robust maintenance and update practices, impeding the sustained functionality of cloud-based systems. Finally, inadequate funding remains a critical obstacle, limiting the ability of libraries to invest in necessary infrastructure and ongoing technological advancements. Adegboire (2010) further explains that hardware breakdown, software problems, unreliable and epileptic power supply, inadequate funding, staff training deficiency, and planned obsolescence of commercial software are part of the challenges facing the automation of libraries. Gbadamosi (2012) posits that bandwidth subscription, daily and routine maintenance of computer sets and lack of steady funding for library services are some challenges facing library automation.

For university libraries in Nigeria to adopt cloud computing technology as a strategy for enhancing effective service delivery of library resources, professionals need to make sure that they understand the cloud components, such as the environment, model and their cloud provider, before placing their digital objects in the cloud for service delivery purposes. To successfully navigate this transition, library professionals need to engage in continuous education and training on cloud computing technologies. This includes developing a comprehensive understanding of various cloud service models (IaaS, PaaS, SaaS), deployment methods (public, private, hybrid), and evaluating potential cloud providers' reliability and security protocols. However, thorough risk assessments and strategic planning are necessary to mitigate potential data privacy, compliance, and interoperability challenges. By equipping themselves with this knowledge and foresight, university libraries in Nigeria can confidently adopt cloud computing solutions, thereby enhancing the efficiency, accessibility, and quality of their service delivery.

Objectives

1. Identify challenges associated with librarians' and IT personnel's adoption and use of Cloud Computing Technology in University Libraries.
2. Determine strategies for enhancing librarians' and IT personnel's adoption and use of Cloud Computing Technology in University Libraries.

Literature Review

As a revolutionary technological framework, cloud computing has fundamentally changed the field of information technology (IT) and how businesses operate worldwide. As defined by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), cloud computing allows easy and widespread access to a shared pool of customizable computing resources. These resources include networks, servers, storage, applications, and services, and can be quickly provided and released with minimal effort or interaction with the service provider (Ogidiaka et al., 2022). The service provides many models, such as Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS), Platform as a Service (PaaS), and Software as a Service (SaaS), which are offered through public, private, hybrid, or community clouds (Mallo & Ogwueleka, 2019).

The adoption of cloud computing has been driven by its numerous advantages, including cost reduction, scalability, and increased operational efficiency. Organizations can significantly reduce their IT infrastructure costs by leveraging cloud services, as they only pay for the resources they consume (Marston et al., 2021). This pay-as-you-go model allows businesses to scale their operations rapidly and efficiently in response to changing market demands (Zhang et al., 2020). Moreover, cloud computing enhances collaboration and accessibility, enabling employees to access data and applications from anywhere via the Internet, thereby increasing productivity and facilitating remote work (Armbrust et al., 2020). However, despite these benefits, data security, privacy, and regulatory compliance concerns continue to pose challenges for widespread cloud adoption, particularly in sectors dealing with sensitive information (Subashini & Kavitha, 2021).

Challenges of Implementing Cloud Technologies in Nigerian Libraries

Implementing cloud technologies in Nigerian libraries presents a unique set of challenges. The potential benefits of cloud computing, such as remote access, multiple user access, and faster response times, are often offset by issues such as:

Erratic power supply – Erratic power supply can significantly hinder the implementation of cloud technologies in libraries (Alouffi, et al 2021). Cloud computing relies on continuous and reliable internet connectivity and electricity to function effectively. In the context of libraries, which are pivotal in providing access to a vast array of digital resources and services, consistent power is essential for maintaining the integrity of cloud-based systems. Interruptions in power supply can lead to disruptions in library services, data loss, and reduced operational efficiency. Moreover, the lack of reliable power can deter libraries from adopting cloud technologies, as the risk of data loss and service interruptions might outweigh the potential benefits. Libraries in areas with unstable power may need to invest in alternative power solutions, such as generators or solar panels, to ensure a stable power supply for their cloud infrastructure. However, this introduces additional costs and complexities in implementing and maintaining cloud technologies. Furthermore, power instability can affect the longevity and reliability of hardware components essential for accessing cloud services, leading to more frequent replacements and higher maintenance costs (Golightly et al., 2022). In regions where power supply is erratic, cloud service providers may also be less inclined to invest, which can limit the options available to libraries. Ultimately, the success of cloud technology implementation

in libraries is closely tied to the stability of the local power infrastructure. Without addressing the power supply issues, libraries may struggle to leverage the full potential of cloud computing to enhance their services and operations.

Low internet bandwidth – Low internet bandwidth significantly hampers the implementation of cloud technologies in libraries, which increasingly depend on high-speed internet for various services. To function effectively, cloud-based applications require robust and reliable internet connections (Golightly et al., 2022). When bandwidth is insufficient, libraries may experience slow service speeds, reduced access to digital resources, and impaired ability to offer new technologies that require high-speed internet, such as streaming media or large-scale data analysis. This can lead to a digital divide, where libraries in areas with low bandwidth cannot provide the same level of service as those with better infrastructure. Consequently, patrons in bandwidth-limited regions may face challenges in accessing information and technology services, which are crucial for education, job searching, and participating in the digital economy.

Absence of experienced personnel – Implementing cloud technologies in libraries is a complex process that requires a blend of technical skills and strategic planning. When libraries lack experienced personnel, they face significant challenges in adopting cloud services effectively. Without skilled staff, libraries may struggle with the technical aspects of cloud migration, such as data transfer, system integration, and configuring cloud-based services to meet the unique needs of their patrons. Furthermore, lacking expertise can lead to an inadequate understanding of cloud security and privacy issues, potentially exposing sensitive user data to risks. The lack of experienced personnel can hinder the library's ability to leverage cloud technologies to improve service delivery, streamline operations, and expand access to digital resources. To address these challenges, libraries might consider investing in training for existing staff, recruiting specialized personnel, or exploring collaborative arrangements where technical responsibilities are shared with institutional IT departments. Ultimately, the successful implementation of cloud technologies in libraries depends on the technology and the people who manage and utilize it.

Financial constraints – Financial constraints significantly impact the implementation of cloud technologies in libraries. Libraries are essential for providing access to a vast range of information resources, and cloud technologies offer a scalable and efficient means to manage and deliver these resources. However, the initial costs of implementing cloud solutions can be substantial. Without adequate funding, libraries may struggle to afford the necessary infrastructure, such as servers and workstations, and the ongoing costs of subscriptions to cloud services. Moreover, budget limitations can hinder the ability to keep up with technological advancements, leading to outdated systems that compromise the quality of service and user experience. The inability to invest in cloud technologies can also limit the library's capacity to provide diverse digital resources, which is crucial for supporting current research and learning opportunities.

Poor technical infrastructure – Poor technical infrastructure can significantly hinder the implementation of cloud technologies in libraries. Libraries with outdated or inadequate technical setups may struggle with the internet bandwidth and hardware requirements for cloud-based services. This can lead to slower system performance, reduced reliability, and frequent downtimes, negatively impacting user experience and service delivery (Chopra, 2021). Moreover, the lack of skilled personnel to manage and troubleshoot advanced cloud technologies can exacerbate these issues, leading to underutilization of cloud capabilities. In regions with limited technical know-how and budgetary allocations for internet access and network tools, libraries may find it challenging to maintain a consistent and secure cloud presence, which is crucial for protecting sensitive data and ensuring seamless access to digital resources. Additionally, without robust technical infrastructure, libraries may be unable to leverage the full spectrum of cloud computing benefits, such as scalability, resource

optimization, and enhanced collaboration, which are essential for modernizing library services and operations.

Security concerns – Security concerns significantly impact the implementation of cloud technologies in libraries. The shift to cloud-based services offers numerous benefits, such as cost savings, flexibility, and enhanced data management. However, it also introduces challenges related to the security and privacy of sensitive data. Libraries must navigate the complexities of protecting digital collections and user information against cyber threats like malware and ransomware attacks (Alouffi et al., 2021; Chopra, 2021). These threats exploit vulnerabilities to access, encrypt, or steal data, often demanding ransom in cryptocurrencies for decryption keys. Libraries are thus compelled to ensure robust security measures, including encryption, access controls, and regular security audits, as part of their cloud technology strategies. Additionally, the integration of cloud services must be managed carefully to maintain interoperability and user trust, ensuring that the adoption of these technologies does not compromise the library's commitment to patron privacy and data protection.

Despite these obstacles, the drive towards digitization and automation of library services is evident, with efforts being made to overcome these hurdles and improve service delivery. Libraries must navigate these challenges effectively to harness the full potential of cloud computing and enhance their role in information dissemination and storage.

Strategies for Enhancing Cloud Computing Technology in Libraries

One of the primary strategies for enhancing library cloud computing is adopting Software as a Service (SaaS) solutions. Makori (2016) highlights that SaaS models allow libraries to access and utilize various applications and services without requiring extensive infrastructure investments. This approach enables libraries to implement advanced catalogue systems, digital asset management tools, and discovery services more efficiently and cost-effectively. Another critical strategy involves leveraging Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) to improve library data management and storage capabilities. Yuvaraj (2016) argues that IaaS solutions provide libraries with scalable and flexible storage options, allowing them to accommodate growing digital collections and meet increasing user demands. This strategy not only enhances data accessibility but also improves disaster recovery and business continuity planning for libraries.

Collaboration and resource sharing represent another crucial strategy for enhancing library cloud computing. Anunobi and Ape (2019) discuss the potential of cloud-based inter-library loan systems and shared digital repositories to facilitate seamless information exchange between institutions. This collaborative approach expands the resources available to library users and promotes cost-sharing among participating libraries. Abdulsalam et al. (2011), in their study on cloud computing as a solution to ICT problems in higher education in Nigeria. The study explored the issues with ICT in Nigeria and its benefits and expected limitations. It suggested a hybrid approach, transitioning some applications and data to cloud computing while leaving others in-house. The study found that cloud computing technology is relatively young and may undergo changes in the future regarding resources, issues, risks, and best practices. However, it offers significant advantages for higher education institutions. Both studies, conducted within Nigeria, focus on the impact of cloud computing in managing ICT challenges. Both studies are similar in their objective and focus on the challenges of ICT management. A significant finding of the study is that cloud computing may have considerable potential to improve the ICT application and infrastructure at higher educational institutions. Considering that the field is still relatively young, it is strongly recommended that early university adopters plan the transition carefully and keep in close contact with organizations that establish industry standards, such as NIST, to ensure a uniform and smooth transition.

Methodology

The study used a descriptive survey design to survey 178 librarians and 13 IT staff from Federal and Private university libraries in North Central, Nigeria. The population consisted of 178 librarians and 13 IT staff. No sampling technique was used due to the manageable size of the population. The instrument used for data collection is a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was developed based on the research questions. The researcher administered the questionnaire with the help of university research assistants. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, with a mean of 2.50 for research questions 7 and 8.

Results and Findings

Research Question One

What are the challenges associated with librarians' and IT personnel's adoption and effective use of Cloud Computing Technology in Federal and Private University Libraries of North Central Nigeria?

Table 1: What challenges are associated with librarians and IT personnel's effective adoption of cloud computing technology in federal and private university libraries in North Central Nigeria?

Challenges	Mean	SD	D
Poor subscription by institutions	3.37	.746	A
Poor Internet network development	3.35	.764	A
Epileptic power supply	3.34	.772	A
Lack of awareness of cloud computing and its application to library services	3.31	.785	A
Poor funding of the library	3.31	.805	A
Lack of orientation program on cloud computing technology services to libraries	3.28	.777	A
Inadequate training of library professionals on emerging technology like cloud	3.25	.807	A
Lack of conceptual clarification of cloud computing technology	3.21	.741	A
Management and staff ignorance of the benefits of cloud computing technology	3.21	.785	A
Inadequate orientation on cloud computing technology	3.20	.830	A
Lack of basic skills for cloud computing technology in library services	3.11	.939	A
Fear of elimination of staff handling the in-house maintenance	3.07	.896	A
Technology phobia among library staff and users	3.05	.944	A
The current economic situation of the country	3.04	.964	A
Inexperience of staff on the job	3.02	.915	A
Staff resistance to change	3.02	.948	A
	3,19	.753	A

The respondents identified 18 challenges associated with cloud computing technology for effective service delivery, with mean values ranging from 3.02 to 3.37. These challenges include poor subscription by institutions, poor internet network development, epileptic power supply, lack of awareness of cloud computing and its application to library services, poor funding, lack of orientation programs, inadequate training of library professionals, conceptual clarification, management and staff ignorance on cloud computing benefits, inadequate

orientation, lack of competence in computer device application, essential skills for cloud computing in library services, high rate of corruption, fear of eliminating staff handling in-house maintenance, technology phobia among library staff and users, current economic situation, inexperience of staff, and resistance to change.

The survey results show that institutions' poor subscription ($X=3.37$) and staff resistance to change ($X=3.02$) are the top challenges associated with cloud computing technology for effective service delivery, with the overall mean ranking these issues as the highest and lowest.

Research Question Two

What are the strategies for enhancing the adoption and effective use of cloud computing technology by librarians and IT personnel in Federal and Private University Libraries of North Central Nigeria?

Table 2: Strategies for enhancing adoption and use of cloud computing technology by librarians and IT personnel in Federal and Private University Libraries of North Central Nigeria?

	Strategies	Mean	SD	R	D
1.	Continuous training of library professionals on emerging technologies as it relates to library services	3.69	.479	1 st .	A
2.	Adequate funding for the library	3.69	.513	1 st	A
3.	Provision of adequate power supply by supporting the system with an inverter	3.68	.500	3 rd	A
4.	A strong internet network should be made available to users	3.68	.485	3 rd	A
5.	Create awareness of cloud computing technology	3.64	.569	5 th	A
6.	Acquire more skills in emerging technology	3.64	.527	5 th	A
7.	Provide orientation program on cloud	3.63	.529	7 th	A
8.	Train and upgrade librarian for competency	3.61	.520	8 th	A
9.	Build the confidence and orientate the psychology of staff on their job security and emerging technology	3.59	.524	9 th	A
10.	Upgrading ICT infrastructure for (IaaS)	3.59	.524	9 th	A
11	Increase bandwidth and library subscription	3.58	.526	11 th	A
12	Encourage librarians and users to embrace technology	3.56	.669	12 th	A
13.	Sensitization on clarification of concept Recruiting the right staff on the job	3.53	.599	13 th	A
14	Proper orientation	3.50	.573	14 th	A
15	The government should seek a lasting solution to improve the economic situation	3.50	.695	14 th	A
16	Checkmate corrupt practices	3.48	.737	16 th	A
17	Regular upgrade of skills	3.47	.599	17 th	A
18	Embrace change	3.47	.705	17 th	A
	<i>Cluster Mean</i>	<i>3.56</i>			

The study reveals that respondents agreed on all strategies for enhancing cloud computing technology for effective library service delivery. The strategies included continuous training of library professionals on emerging technologies, adequate funding, power supply, strong internet networks, creating awareness on cloud computing, acquiring more skills, providing orientation programs, training and upgrading librarians, building staff confidence, upgrading ICT infrastructure for IaaS, increasing bandwidth and library subscriptions, encouraging librarians and users to embrace technology, sensitization on clarifying concepts, recruiting the right staff, proper orientation, seeking lasting solutions to improve the economic situation,

checking corrupt practices, regular skill upgrades, and embracing change. The overall mean ranking for continuous training of library professionals on emerging technologies was 3.69, while embracing change was ranked lowest. The respondents agreed that all these strategies can help enhance cloud computing technology for effective library service delivery.

Summary of Findings

The summary of findings for this study is presented under each of the research questions and tested hypotheses. The following emerged from the data analysis and interpretation of the results.

1. The challenges associated with the application of cloud computing technology for effective service delivery in University Libraries in North Central, Nigeria, anchor around poor institutional subscription, poor internet network development, epileptic power supply, and lack of awareness of cloud computing and its application to library services, among others.
2. Strategies for enhancing cloud computing for effective library services delivery include continuous training of library professionals on emerging technologies as they relate to library services, adequate funding of the library, provision of adequate power supply by supporting the system with an inverter, strong internet network should be made available to users, create awareness on cloud computing technology, acquire more skills on emerging technology among others.

Discussion of Findings

The challenges associated with cloud computing technology for effective service delivery

The study identified 18 challenges librarians and IT staff face in implementing cloud computing technology for effective library service delivery, including poor subscription, internet network development, power supply issues, fear of staff elimination, economic situation, inexperience, and resistance to change. Gbadamosi (2012) identified bandwidth subscription, daily computer maintenance, and lack of steady funding as challenges. Miller (2008), Jeffrey and Neidecker-Lutz (2009), and Ristenpart et al. (2009) identified challenges in cloud computing, including lack of constant internet connection, slow internet connections, limited features, security, and the risk of data loss or cloud vendor bankruptcy. Corrado (2011) supplements the arguments when they claim that the services libraries can acquire through cloud computing platforms may be valuable. However, the cost of internet access, even if bandwidth is not currently at a premium, can become- a considerable hurdle to adequate provision of services”.

However, commenting on the challenges associated with cloud computing, some scholars remark that the biggest impediment to cloud computing will not be technological but attitudinal. Alvarez (2011), in concern and challenges in adopting cloud computing for small and medium entrepreneurs and large companies in Japan, pointed out that security is a barrier for firms moving to incorporate cloud service and that there is a lack of surveys in the field. More so, Akin, Temilayo and Daramola (2014), the impact and challenges of cloud computing adoption on public universities in South-Western Nigeria revealed that the reluctance of few institutions to expand the use of cloud services has been concerned with privacy security and the potential of perceived risk associated with intellectual contents.

Strategies for enhancing cloud computing technology for effective service delivery

The study suggests strategies for improving library services, including continuous training of professionals on emerging technologies, adequate funding, power supply, strong internet networks, awareness of cloud computing, and training librarians for competency. It also emphasizes the importance of upgrading ICT infrastructure, increasing bandwidth, and library

subscriptions to encourage technology adoption. It also calls for proper orientation, sensitization on concept clarification, and recruitment of the right staff. The government should seek lasting solutions to improve the economic situation, combat corrupt practices, and regularly upgrade skills to embrace change. Goldner (2012) and Geoffery (2013) argue that libraries can benefit from cloud computing technology to address hardware breakdowns, software problems, and staff training deficiencies, allowing them to focus on innovation and patron services. Data can be easily shared among users, eliminating the need for local storage, maintenance, and backup. However, Khajeh and Sriram (2010) emphasize the need for regular training for library professionals and stakeholders on cloud technology due to its interdisciplinary nature. Fryer and Brown (2010) suggest further research to determine the economic reality of cloud adoption. Han (2015) emphasizes the need for information professionals to consider potential data transfer fees, which can significantly impact cloud storage costs.

Lastly, Robinson (2015) focuses more on trust and confidence as essential factors for consideration. This is to prevent and protect against hackers. The author suggests it is crucial for the Heads of Library Schools, University Authority, and other organizations to encourage Librarians and IT staff to attend workshops, short-term courses, seminars, conferences, etc., for effective services to improve to a certain degree from the current state. The current study exposes that Librarians and IT staff working in the library possess considerable basic ICT skills to apply the cloud to library services. Still, there is enough room to improve and enhance their ICT skills and apply them to provide emerging ICT-based library services. Below are some suggestions.

Recommendations

Considering the findings and implications of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. University library funding should be increased to enable it to upgrade to modern ICT infrastructures, which will aid it in providing effective services that meet societal information needs.
2. Libraries should improve their bandwidth subscription and internet connectivity to enhance effective and quality service delivery on the cloud.
3. Librarians and IT staff need to be proactive and empower themselves to meet the challenges of modern library design and demand, respectively.
4. The library curriculum needs to be reviewed for the Library school to empower the upcoming librarians to deploy the cloud effectively for service delivery and library management.

Conclusion

The study ascertained that poor subscription, poor internet network development, epileptic power supply, poor funding, lack of basic skills for cloud computing technology in library services, lack of conceptual clarification, and lack of competence in the application of computer devices were identified as significant challenges associated with the application of cloud computing technology for effective service delivery in university libraries. The strategies for enhancing these challenges are increasing bandwidth and internet subscription, providing strong internet networks, providing adequate power supply and funding, and acquiring new skills in cloud computing technology in library services, among others.

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